

Pediatric Posterior Fossa Medulloblastoma with Multifocal Intracranial Extension: Clinical Case Report

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Abstract:

Medulloblastoma is the most common malignant brain tumour affecting children. These tumours are high grade with propensity to metastasize within the central nervous system and, less frequently, outside the neuraxis. Recent advancements in molecular subgrouping of medulloblastoma refine diagnosis and improve counseling in regards to overall prognosis. Both are predicated on the molecular drivers of each subgroup—WNT-activated, SHH-activated, group 3, and group 4. The traditional treatment for medulloblastoma includes a multimodal approach with surgery, radiation, and multiagent chemotherapy. Certainly, the known neurological, developmental, endocrine, and psychosocial injury related to medulloblastoma and its associated therapies motivate ongoing research towards improving treatment for this life-threatening tumour while at the same time minimizing long-term side effects. We found a case presenting with posterior fossa medulloblastoma with multifocal intracranial drop metastasis hence making it a rare case with a challenging approach towards its management.

Keyword: Medulloblastoma, Multifocal Drop Metastasis, Transvermian Approach.

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Introduction

Clinical Case Presentation:

A 10 years old male child came to Gauhati medical college and hospital OPD at Neurosurgery department with chief complaints of headache and nausea since one month. Also reduced appetite since one month. On examination, patients general examination was within normal limits as well as cranial nerve and motor examination was within normal limits, No cerebellar signs seen. We

advised for a NCCT head followed by MRI brain with following reports:

A fairly well-defined lesion is seen in fourth ventricle appearing heterogeneously hyperintense on T2/FLAIR image, hypointense on T1WI and shows few patchy areas of restriction of diffusion on DWI images with corresponding reduced ADC values.

Figure 1: Sagittal section

Figure 2: T1 Contrast Image

Figure 3: T2 Flair Image

Multiple Discrete and conglomerate enhancing drop metastasis are seen along the dural surface of bilateral cerebral hemisphere, bilateral tentorium cerebelli, interhemispheric fissure, bilateral sylvian fissure and along left cerebellar hemisphere also mets in right anterior temporal lobe.

Figure 4: T1 Contrast Image

Surgical Management:

After meticulous examination and concerned investigation, we went ahead with Classical Midline suboccipital craniotomy and excision of tumour. Intraoperatively, suboccipital craniotomy was done and dura opened in T shape manner, cisterna magna drained, we found two lesions on either cerebellum around 2*1 cm each and shown in image.

Excision was done and separate samples were sent for biopsy. Traditional Trans-vermian approach carried out and tumour was found emerging from fourth ventricle with invasion into brainstem.

Tumour was seen as reddish pink colour, moderately vascular, non-friable or suckable and adherent to brainstem. Tumour excision was done and part of tumour was left behind near brainstem.

Figure 5: Tumour in left cerebellar hemisphere with its diagrammatic representation

Figure 6: Tumour in right cerebellar hemisphere with its diagrammatic representation

Figure 7: Tumour arising from 4th ventricle

Samples sent for biopsy separately.

Figure 8: Post-operative image

Figure 9: Postoperative wound site

Histopathology:

Figure 10: HPE slide showing abnormal blood vessels with Grade 4 tumour cells within

Figure 11: HPE slide showing abnormal arrangement of Grade 4 tumour cells

Figure 10 and 11 are the biopsy specimens taken from cerebellar hemispheres.

Follow up: Patient was followed up for one month post operatively and was sent for radiation.

Discussion:

Medulloblastoma is tumour of the pediatric age and account for 30 percent of all intracranial tumours in children [3]. They are less commonly seen in adults (1% of all intracranial tumors, 25-34% of all medulloblastomas.[1,4,6]. Almost 75% arise from the midline and extend into the 4th ventricle. In older children and adults, half of them are located in the cerebellum.

More than two-thirds of the tumour shows involvement of the central nervous system (CNS). Metastasis occurs by pathway of CSF and Virchow-Robin spaces [6]. They are usually unilocular and multifocal involvement is extremely rare. We have found only three cases in the literature. [2,7,8]. In our case, we found midline 4th ventricle tumour which histopathology came to be medulloblastoma with surrounding bilateral cerebellar tumours whose histopathology came to be Grade 4 embryonal tumour ie medulloblastoma.

We suspected these two cerebellar tumours to be histo-pathologically different but they we proved as drop metastasis of medulloblastoma, Also there are multiple drop metastasis in bilateral cerebral hemisphere one being in right temporal lobe which are rarely found in medulloblastoma. In our case there was no spinal drop metastasis seen. Shen et al. [7] and Spagnoli et al. [8] could not explain completely the multifocal medulloblastoma in cerebellum. These two authors could not decide that, these lesions occur at the same time or by the

cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) seeding. But Gliomroth et al. [2] have reported that, in addition to cerebellar localization, since there was occipital lesion, CSF-seeding could be the cause. It is said that, medulloblastomas arise from embryological cells located roof of the 4th ventricle [5] and if they have multifocal cerebellar as well as cerebral involvement, the lesions may be due to the interruption of the migration of the embryological cells from the external granular layer.

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